

ALGEBRAICNESS PROPERTIES ON TRANSITIVE BINARY RELATIONAL SETS AND A CHARACTERIZATION OF CONTINUOUS DIRECTED COMPLETE POSETS

MOHAMMED M. KHALAF* AND ESMAIL HASSAN ABDULLATIF AL-SABRI

ABSTRACT. In this work we introduce and study the concepts of algebraicness, and continuity on transitive binary relational sets (so called TRS). Some interactions between these concepts are investigated. Further more a characterization of continuous directed complete posets and Algebraic TRS are studied. Our results are generalizations of corresponding results in posets.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is interstet to mention that in 1994 [1], S. Abramsky and A. Jung considered the concepts of continuous directed complete posets (continuous domain) and algebraic domains. R. Hekmann considered and studies these concepts in detail in this paper [5]. Continuous posets were introduced and studied independently by R. E. Hoffmann [2,6,7,8], J. D. Lawson [11,12] and in more fashion by G. Markowsky [14] and M. Erne [3]. It is worth to mention that J. Nino-Salcedo, considered and studied in more details the concepts of continuous posets and algebraic posets in this paper [15]. In fact the concept of continuous poset (resp., algebraic poset) in the sense of J. Nino-Salcedo [15] and the concep of continuous. In [18], H. Zhang studied a type of continuous poset which is a generalization of continuous poset in the sense of J. Nino-Salcedo [15]. In [5], the concepts of bounded complete posets, bounded complete domains, finitely complete posets, finitely complete domains are studied. It worth to mention that H. Zhang [18] studied some interactions between bounded complete domains and scott-topology and lawson topology. Our aims here is devoted to introduce and study the continuity and algebraicness properties of TRS . Our results extended the corresponding results in posets and domains [5,9,15,18]. In section 2 we explain the concepts of a continuous TRS , the relations between lower (resp. upper) closure in X of A and when x below (resp. y is way above) y (resp. x) directed subset of X . Also, prove that a if A $TRS (X, \leq)$ is continuous poset in the sence of H. Zhang (resp., continuous poset in the sence of J. Nino-Salcedo, continuous domain in the sence of R. Hekmann), then the way relation below ' \ll ' is continuous information system, Finally take about when the way relation below ' \ll ' is interpolative and a subset B of a poset (X, \leq) is called a base for X . In this section 3 we prove if TRS equivalent domain, i.e., a poset in which

2010 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 03E72; 18B30; 54A40.

Key words and phrases. algebraicness, transitive binary relational sets, poset.

Received: February 15, 2023. Accepted: March 15, 2023. Published: March 31, 2023.

*Corresponding author.

every directed subset has a supremum, then a continuous domain in the sense of R. Hekmann and continuous TRS are identical.

Definition 1.1. Let $A \subseteq X$. Then:

(1) A subset A of the domain [5] (resp. Poset) X is called directed closed (d -closed for short) iff \forall directed subset D of A , $\bigvee(D) \in A$;

(2) A subset A of the Poset X is called Scott-closed iff A is d -closed lower subset of X [15];

(3) A is called d -(resp. Scott-) open iff A^c d -(resp. Scott-) closed [5,15];

(4) Let $x, y \in X$. We say x below (resp. y is way above) y (resp. x), denoted by $x \ll y$ iff $\forall D \subseteq X$, s.t. D is directed subset of X with $\bigvee D$ exists and $y \leq \bigvee D$, $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $x \leq d$. The family of all elements in X each of which way above (resp. way below) x is denoted and defined as follows: $\uparrow x = \{y \in X : x \ll y\}$ (resp. $\downarrow x = \{y \in X : y \ll x\}$) [15];

(5) Let $x \in X$. If $x \ll x$, then x is said to be isolated. The family of all isolated points above (resp. below) $x \in X$ is denoted and defined by: $\uparrow^\circ x = \{y \in X : y \ll x \text{ and } x \leq y\}$ (resp. $\downarrow^\circ x = \{y \in X : y \ll x \text{ and } y \leq x\}$) [15].

Proposition 1.1 (Proposition 6.4.7 [5], Lemma 2.15(i)[16]) Let X be a continuous domain, then for every two points $x, z \in X$ with $x \ll z$ there is a point $y \in X$ s.t., $x \ll y \ll z$.

Proposition 1.2 (Proposition 1.17 [18]). Let X be a continuous poset in the sense of Zhang, then for every two points $x, z \in X$ with $x \ll z$ there is a point $y \in X$ s.t., $x \ll y \ll z$.

Proposition 1.3 (Proposition 6.7.2 [5] and Lemma 2.14[15]) If (X, \leq) is continuous domain in the sense of R. Hekmann iff X is a continuous poset in the sense of J. Nino-Salcedo.

Proposition 1.4 (Proposition 6.2.2 [5]) A domain X is an algebraic in the sense of R. Hekmann iff it is algebraic poset in the sense of J. Nino-Salcedo.

Theorem 1.1 (Proposition 6.7.3 [5]). If X is an algebraic domain then, it is a continuous domain.

Definition 1.2. Let $A \subseteq X$. Then:

(1) A is called directed subset of X iff $A \neq \phi$ and $\forall x, y \in A$, $\exists z \in A$ s.t. $x \leq z$ and $y \leq z$ [5];

(2) The lower (resp. upper) closure in X of A is denoted by $\downarrow A$ (resp. $\uparrow A$) and defined as follows: $\downarrow A = \{x \in X : \exists y \in A \text{ s.t. } x \leq y\}$ (resp. $\uparrow A = \{x \in X : \exists y \in A \text{ s.t. } y \leq x\}$) [5]

(3) The convex hull A is denoted by $\updownarrow A$ and defined as follows: $\updownarrow A = \downarrow A \cap \uparrow A$ [5];

(4) Let $A, B \subseteq X$. B is called cofinal in A iff $B \subseteq A \subseteq \downarrow(B)$ [5].

Definition 1.3. Let ' \leq' ' be a binary relation set on $X \neq \phi$. Then;

(1) ' \leq' ' is called reflexive iff $\forall x \in X$, $x \leq x$ [13];

(2) ' \leq' ' is called antisymmetric iff $\forall x, y \in X$, $x \leq y$ and $y \leq x \Rightarrow x = y$ [13];

(3) ' \leq' ' is called transitive iff $\forall x, y, z \in X$, $x \leq y$ and $y \leq z \Rightarrow x \leq z$ [13];

(4) ' \leq' ' is called symmetric iff $\forall x, y \in X$, $x \leq y \Rightarrow y \leq x$ [13];

(5) ' \leq' is called interpolative iff $\forall x, z \in X$, with $x \leq z$, $\exists y \in X$ s.t. $x \leq y \leq z$ [5, 16].

(6) if ' \leq' satisfies the conditions (1), (2) and (3), then (X, \leq) is called Partially order set (Poset) [13];

(7) if ' \leq' satisfies the conditions (1), and (3), then (X, \leq) is called pre-orderd set (Quasi set)[13];

(8) if ' \leq' satisfies the conditions (1), (2), (3) and (4), then (X, \leq) is called an equivalence set,

(9) if ' \leq' satisfies the conditions (3) and (5), then (X, \leq) is a continuous information system [10,16].

(10) if ' \leq' satisfies the conditions (3), and $\forall x \in X$, and for every finite subset A of X the following axiom holds: if $\forall y \in A$, $y \leq x$ then $\exists z \in X$ s.t. $\forall y \in A$, $y \leq z$ and $z \leq x$, then (X, \leq) is abstract basis [17].

2. Continuous TRS

Here in this section explain the concepts of a continuous TRS , the relations between lower (resp. upper) closure in X of A and when x below (resp. y is way above) y (resp. x), directed subset of X . Also, prove that a if A $TRS (X, \leq)$ is continuous poset in the sence of H. Zhang (resp., continuous poset in the sence of J. Nino-Salcedo, continuous domain in the sence of R. Hekmann), then the way relation below ' \ll' is continuous information system, Finally take about when the way relation below ' \ll' is interpolative and a subset B of a poset (X, \leq) is called a base for X .

Definition 2.1. A $TRS (X, \leq)$ is continuous TRS iff $\forall x \in X$, the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) $\bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$
- (2) $\downarrow x$ be a directed subset of X , and
- (3) $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(\bigcup\{\bigvee(\downarrow a) : a \in \downarrow x\}))$.

Theorem 2.1. Let (X, \leq) be a TRS . let $x, y, z \in X$. Then :

- (1) If $x \leq y$ and $y \ll z$, then $x \ll z$;
- (2) If $x \ll y$ and $y \leq z$, then $x \ll z$;
- (3) If $\bigvee(\{y\}) \neq \phi$. and $x \ll y$, then $x \leq y$;
- (4) If $\bigvee(\{y\}) \neq \phi$. or $\bigvee(\{z\}) \neq \phi$, $x \ll y$ and $y \ll z$, then $x \ll z$.

Proof (1) Let D be a directed subset of X s.t. $z \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Then $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $y \leq d$. Then $x \leq d$ and hence $x \ll z$.

(2) Let D be a directed subset of X s.t. $z \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Then $\exists k \in \bigvee(D)$ s.t. $z \leq k$. Thus $y \leq k$ and so $y \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Therefore $\exists l \in D$ s.t. $x \leq l$. hence $x \ll z$.

(3) Let $D = \{y\}$ and assume that $x \ll y$. Then $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $x \leq d$ but $y = d$. Thus $x \leq y$;

(4) The proof follow directly From (1) and (3) above.

Lemma 2.1 Let (X, \leq) be a TRS , let $\downarrow x$ be a directed subset of $\forall x \in X$. Then $\forall z \in X$, $D = \bigcup\{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow z\}$ is called directed subset.

Proof Let $\lambda, \mu \in D$ s.t., $\lambda \neq \mu$. Then $a_1, a_2 \in \Downarrow z$ s.t., $\lambda \in \Downarrow a_1$ and $\mu \in \Downarrow a_2$. If $a_1 = a_2$, the result holds. otherwise let $a \in \text{ub}(\{a_1, a_2\}) \cap \Downarrow z$ so that Theorem 2.1 (2). $\lambda, \mu \in \Downarrow a$. Since $\Downarrow a$ is called directed subset, then $\exists \rho \in \text{ub}(\{\lambda, \mu\}) \cap \Downarrow a \subseteq \text{ub}(\{\lambda, \mu\}) \cap D$. Thus D is called directed subset.

Lemma 2.2. Let (X, \leq) be a *TRS*, let $\forall x \in X$. Then $\forall x \in X$, $\text{ub}(\bigcup\{\Downarrow a : a \in \Downarrow x\}) = \text{ub}(\bigcup\{\bigvee(\Downarrow a) : a \in \Downarrow x\})$. Thus $\bigvee(\bigcup\{\Downarrow a\}) = \bigvee(\bigcup\{\bigvee(\Downarrow a) : a \in \Downarrow x\})$.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda \in \text{ub}(\bigcup\{\Downarrow a : a \in \Downarrow x\}) &\Leftrightarrow \forall \mu \in \bigcup\{\Downarrow a : a \in \Downarrow x\}, \\ \lambda \geq \mu &\Leftrightarrow \forall \mu \in (\Downarrow a), a \in (\Downarrow x), \\ \lambda \geq \mu &\Leftrightarrow \forall \rho \in \bigvee(\Downarrow a), a \in (\Downarrow x), \\ \lambda \geq \rho &\Leftrightarrow \lambda \in \text{ub}(\bigcup\{\bigvee(\Downarrow a) : a \in \Downarrow x\}). \end{aligned}$$

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.1 and Proposition 1.2 (Proposition 6.4.7 [5], Lemma 2.15(i)[16] and Proposition 1.17 [18]).

Theorem 2.2. If (X, \leq) is continuous *TRS*, then the way relation below ' \ll ' is interpolative, i.e., $\forall x, z \in X$, with $x \leq z$, implies that $\exists y \in X$ s.t. $x \ll y \ll z$.

Proof. From Lemma 2.1 and 2.2, $z \in \Downarrow (\bigvee(\bigcup\{\Downarrow y : y \in \Downarrow z\}))$ and $\bigcup\{\Downarrow y : y \in \Downarrow z\}$ is directed. Then $\exists d \in \Downarrow y$ for some $y \in \Downarrow z$ s.t., $x \leq d$. From Theorem 2.1.(1), we have $x \ll y$. Hence $x \ll y \ll z$.

Theorem 2.3. If (X, \leq) is continuous *TRS*, then the way relation below ' \ll ' is continuous information system.

Proof. From Theorem 2.1.(4). and Theorem 2.2.

Corollary 2.1 If (X, \leq) is continuous poset in the sence of H. Zhang (resp., continuous poset in the sence of J. Nino-Salcedo, continuous domain in the sence of R. Heckmann), then the way relation below ' \ll ' is continuous information system.

Lemma 2.3. For any (X, \leq) *TRS*. if $\forall x \in X$, $\bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$, and the way relation below ' \ll ' is interpolative, then $\forall x \in X$, $\Downarrow x = \bigcup\{\Downarrow a : a \in \Downarrow x\}$.

Proof Let $z \in \bigcup\{\Downarrow a : a \in \Downarrow x\}$. Then $\exists a \in \Downarrow x$ s.t., $z \ll a$. From From Theorem 2.1.(4), $z \ll x$, i.e., $z \in \Downarrow x$. Second, let $z \in \Downarrow x$. Then $z \ll x$. Since ' \ll ' is interpolative, $\exists a \in X$ s.t., $z \ll a \ll x$, i.e., $z \in \bigcup\{\Downarrow a : a \in \Downarrow x\}$.

Applying Lemma 2.3., Theorem 2.2. and Theorem 2.3. one have the following theorem.

Theorem 2.4. A *TRS* (X, \leq) is continuous iff the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) The way relation below ' \ll ' is interpolative
- (2) $\forall x \in X$, $\bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$;
- (3) $\forall x \in X$, $\Downarrow x$ is directed ;

$$(4) \forall x \in X, x \in \downarrow \bigvee(\downarrow x).$$

Proof First of all, we note that conditions (2) and (3) above are common.

\implies : From Theorem 2.2., ' \ll' is interpolative so that conditions (1) above is satisfied. From Lemma 2.3., conditions (4) above is satisfied.

\impliedby : From Lemma 2.3., one can have that conditions (3) in Definition 2.1

Corollary 2.2 A TRS (X, \leq) is continuous domain in the sence of R. Hekmann (resp., continuous poset in the sence of H. Zhang), if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) The way relation below ' \ll' is interpolative
- (2) $\forall x \in X, \downarrow x$ is directed ;
- (3) $\forall x \in X, x \in \downarrow \bigvee(\downarrow x)$.

Proposition 2.1. Let $\lambda, \mu \in X$. If μ directed subset and cofinal in λ , then λ is directed subset and $\bigvee(\lambda) = \bigvee(\mu)$.

Theorem 2.5.A TRS (X, \leq) is continuous if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) The way relation below ' \ll' is interpolative
- (2) $\forall x \in X, \bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$;
- (3) $\forall x \in X, \exists$ a directed subset D of $\downarrow x$ s.t., $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$.

Proof \implies : From Theorem 2.4., conditions (1) and (2) are satisfied. The condition (3) is satisfied if we put $D = \downarrow x$.

\impliedby : Now conditions (1) and (2) are satisfied in Theorem 2.4. are given above. We need to prove that D is cofinal in $\downarrow x$. First $D \subseteq \downarrow x$ and D is directed . Second, let $y \in \downarrow x$. Since $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$, then $\exists d \in D$ s.t., $y \leq d$. So, $y \in \downarrow (D)$. Then from Proposition 2.1, $\downarrow x$ is directed and $\bigvee(\downarrow x) = \bigvee(D)$. Hence conditions (3) and (4) in Theorem 2.4. are satisfied.

Corollary 2.3 A TRS (X, \leq) is continuous domain in the sence of R. Hekmann (resp., continuous poset in the sence of H. Zhang), if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) The way relation below ' \ll' is interpolative
- (2) $\forall x \in X, \exists$ a directed subset D of $\downarrow x$ s.t., $x = \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.3 (Proposition 6.7.2 [5] and Lemma 2.14[15]).

Theorem 2.6.A TRS (X, \leq) is continuous if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) $\forall x \in X, \bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$;
- (2) $\forall x \in X, \exists$ a directed subset D of $\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$. s.t., $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$.

Proof \implies : From Theorem 2.5., and Lemma 2.3. on can have that $\downarrow x = \bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$ so that from conditions (3) in Theorem 2.5 on have directly conditions (2) in above.

\impliedby : Since D is cofinal in $\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$ (Indeed, $D \subseteq \bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$ let $z \in \bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$. $z \ll a$ from some $a \in \downarrow x$ so that from From Theorem 2.1.(4). $z \ll x$ Since D is directed and $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$, then $\exists d \in D$ s.t., $z \leq d$. i.e., $z \in \downarrow (D)$.), then from Proposition 2.1, $\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$ is directed and $\bigvee(D) = \bigvee(\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\})$. Hence conditions (3) in Theorem 2.5 is satisfied. Also,

one can prove that ' \ll' is interpolative (Indeed, $x \ll z$ and from conditions (2) above $z \in \downarrow (\bigvee (\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}))$). Thus $\exists d \in \bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$ s.t., $x \leq d \ll a \ll z$. So, From From Theorem 2.1.(1), $x \ll a$. Then $x \ll a \ll z$). Then conditions (2) in Theorem 2.5 is satisfied. Hence A $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is continuous.

Corollary 2.4 A $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is continuous poset in the sence of in the sence of H. Zhang iff $\forall x \in X, \exists$ directed subset D of $\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$ s.t., $x = \bigvee(D)$.

Definition 2.2. A subset B of X is called a base for X if the following conditions are satisfied:

- 1) $\forall x \in X, \bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$;
- 2) $\forall x \in X, \exists$ a directed subset D of B s.t., $D \subseteq \bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$. and $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$

Theorem 2.7.A $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is continuous iff it has a base.

Proof \implies : From Theorem 2.6, $B = \bigcup_{x \in X} (\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\})$;

\impliedby : Conditions (2) in Theorem 2.6 is satisfied directly from the definition of the base of a $TRIS (X, \leq)$.

Corollary 2.5 Let $TRIS (X, \leq)$ be a domain. X is a continuous domain in the sence of in the sence of R. Hekmann (continuous poset in the sence of J. Nino-Salcedo,)

Definition 2.3. A subset B of a poset (X, \leq) is called a base for X iff $\forall x \in X, \exists$ a directed subset D of $\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}$ s.t., $\bigvee(D)$ exists and $x = \bigvee(D)$.

Corollary 2.6 A poset (X, \leq) is a continuous domain in the sence of in the sence of H. Zhang iff it has a base (as in Definition 2.3.).

3. A characterization of continuous directed complete posets and Algebraic $TRIS$.

In this section we prove if $TRIS \iff$ domain, i.e., a poset in which every directed subset has a supremum, then a continuous domain in the sence of in the sence of R. Hekmann and continuous $TRIS$ are identical.

Theorem 3.1. Let (X, \leq) be a $TRIS$. let $x, y, z \in X$. Then :

- (1) If $x \leq y$ and $y \ll z$, then $x \ll z$;
- (2) If $x \ll y$ and $y \leq z$, then $x \ll z$;
- (3) If $\bigvee(\{y\}) \neq \phi$. and $x \ll y$, then $x \leq y$;
- (4) If $\bigvee(\{y\}) \neq \phi$. or $\bigvee(\{z\}) \neq \phi$, $x \ll y$ and $y \ll z$, then $x \ll z$.

Proof (1) Let D be a directed subset of X s.t. $z \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Then $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $y \leq d$. Then $x \leq d$ and hence $x \ll z$.

(2) Let D be a directed subset of X s.t. $z \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Then $\exists k \in \bigvee(D)$ s.t. $z \leq k$. Thus $y \leq k$ and so $y \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Therefore $\exists l \in D$ s.t. $x \leq l$. hence $x \ll z$.

(3) Let $D = \{y\}$ and assume that $x \ll y$. Then $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $x \leq d$ but $y = d$. Thus $x \leq y$;

(4) The proof follow directly From (1) and (3) above.

Lemma 3.1 If (X, \leq) is a continuous TRS and ' \leq' ' is antisymmetric, then:

(1) The supremum of any set is unique whenever it exist; and

(2) $\forall x \in X, x = \bigvee(\downarrow x)$.

Proof (1) Obvious;

(2) From Theorem 2.4(4), $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(\downarrow x))$, so that $x \leq \bigvee(\{\downarrow x\})$. Conversely, $\forall \lambda \in (\downarrow x), \lambda \ll x$. From Theorem 3.1(3), $\forall \lambda \in (\downarrow x), \lambda \leq x$ so that $\bigvee((\downarrow x)) \leq x$

Lemma 3.2 If TRS (X, \leq) is a continuous and if ' \leq' ' is reflexive, then a subset D of X is a directed subset iff $\forall x, y \in D, \exists z \in \text{ub}(\{x, y\}) \cap D$.

Proof \implies : Let $\{x, y\} \subseteq D$ s.t., $x = y$. Since ' \leq' ' is reflexive, then $x \in \text{ub}(\{x, y\}) \cap D$,
 \Leftarrow : Obvious.

Theorem 3.2. Let A TRS (X, \leq) is a continuous domain in the sence of in the sence of R. Hekmann (continuous poset in the sence of J. Nino-Salcedo,) iff A TRS (X, \leq) is a continuous domain with ' \leq' ' is reflexive and antisymmetric.

Proof From Lemma 3.1, Lemma 3.2 and Definition 2.1. the proof is obtained.

Definition 3.1.A TRS (X, \leq) is algebraic iff the following conditions are satisfied:

(1) $\forall x \in X, \downarrow_o x$ is directed subset of X , and

(2) $\forall x \in X, x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(\downarrow_o x))$

Theorem 3.3. If a TRS (X, \leq) is algebraic, then ' \leq' ' is interpolative.

Proof Let $x, z \in X$ s.t., $x \ll z$. Then condition (2) above implies that from fact $z \in \downarrow (\bigvee(\downarrow_o z))$, $\exists l \in \downarrow_o z$ s.t., $x \leq l$. Since $l \ll l$ and $x \leq l$, then from From Theorem 3.1(1), (2), $\exists l \in X$ s.t., $x \ll l \ll z$.

Theorem 3.4. If a TRS (X, \leq) is algebraic, then (X, \ll) is continuous information system.

Proof Applying Theorem 3.3, it rests to prove that ' \ll' ' is transitive. Let $x, y, z \in X$ s.t., $x \ll y$ and $y \ll z$. Since $y \ll z$ and $z \in \downarrow (\bigvee(\downarrow_o z))$, then $\exists l \in \downarrow_o z$ s.t., $y \ll l$. Since $l \in (\downarrow_o z)$ then $l \leq z$ so that $y \leq z$. Now, $x \ll y$ and $y \leq z$, then from From Theorem 3.1(2), we have that $x \ll z$.

Remark3.1. In from Theorem 3.1(4), we need the property that $\forall x \in X, \bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$, to prove that ' \ll' ' is transitive for a continuous TRS but as we illustrate in the proof of Theorem 3.4 we do not need this property to prove that ' \ll' ' is transitive for an a TRS algebraic.

Corollary 3.1 If a $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is algebraic domain in the sence of in the sence of R. Hekmann (resp., algebraic domain in the sence of J. Nino-Salcedo,), then (X, \ll) is continuous information system.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.4 (Proposition 6.2.2 [5]).

Theorem 3.4. A $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is algebraic, iff $\forall x \in X, \exists$ a directed subset D of $\downarrow_o x$ s.t., $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$.

Proof \Leftarrow : $\forall x \in X$, take $D = \downarrow_o x$. Then the result holds.

\Rightarrow : Let $x \in X$. We need to prove that D is cofinal in $\downarrow_o x$. Now , $D \subseteq \downarrow_o x$. Let $z \in \downarrow_o x$. So that from Theorem 3.1(2) $z \ll x$. Since $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D))$, $\exists d \in D$ s.t., $z \leq d$. Thus $z \in \downarrow D$. Hence from Proposition 2.1 the result holds..

Theorem 3.5. A $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is algebraic, then

- (1) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \downarrow_o x \subseteq \downarrow_o y$
- (2) $\downarrow_o x \subseteq \downarrow_o y \Rightarrow \forall z \in (\bigvee(\downarrow_o y)), x \leq z$.

Proof (1) Let $x \leq y$ and let $z \in \downarrow_o x$. Then $z \ll z$ and $z \leq x$ so that $z \ll z$ and $z \leq y$ so that $z \in \downarrow_o y$

(2) Suppose $\downarrow_o x \subseteq \downarrow_o y$. Then $\forall l \in (\bigvee(\downarrow_o x)), \forall z \in (\bigvee(\downarrow_o y)), l \leq z$. Since $x \in (\bigvee(\downarrow_o x))$, then $\exists l_o \in (\bigvee(\downarrow_o x))$ s.t., $x \in l_o$. So, $\forall z \in (\bigvee(\downarrow_o y)), x \leq z$.

Corollary 3.2 If a $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is algebraic domain and ' \leq' is antisymmetric, then $x \leq y$ iff $\downarrow_o x \subseteq \downarrow_o y$.

Proof \Leftarrow : Since ' \leq' is antisymmetric and X is domain , then $\bigvee(\downarrow_o y)$ exists and unique, say equal z . Since X is algebraic, then $z = y$. Thus from Theorem 3.5 (2), the results holds.

\Rightarrow : It follows fr (1) in Theorem 3.5.

The corollary 3.2 is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 6.2.3 [5] since the reflexivity of ' \leq' is not assumed.

Theorem 3.6. If $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is algebraic, then:

$$\forall x \in X, \exists \text{ a directed subset } D \text{ of } \downarrow_o x \text{ s.t., } x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(D)).$$

Proof If we prove that $\forall x \in X, \downarrow_o x \subseteq \downarrow_o x$. The result holds. So let $z \in \downarrow_o x$. Then $z \ll z$ and $z \leq x$. Then from Theorem 3.1 (2), $z \in \downarrow_o x$.

The Theorem 3.6 is a generalization of the corresponding result in Theorem 1.1 (Proposition 6.7.3 [5]).

Corollary 3.3 If a $TRIS (X, \leq)$ is algebraic and $\forall x \in X, \bigvee(\{x\}) \neq \phi$, then (X, \leq) is continuous

Definition 3.2.In $TRIS (X, \leq)$, $\forall x \in X, x \ll x$, then x is said to be isolated and we can write $x \in \mathbf{K}(X)$.

Theorem 3.7. For $TRIS (X, \leq)$ assume that the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) $\forall x \in X$, $\downarrow x$ is directed subset ;
- (2) $\forall x \in X$, $x \in \downarrow (\bigvee(\downarrow x))$;
- (3) $\forall x \in X$, $x \ll y$, $\exists k \in \mathbf{K}(X)$ s.t., $x \leq k \leq y$. Then (X, \leq) is algebraic.

Proof We need to prove that $\forall x \in X$, $\downarrow_{\circ} x$ is cofinal in $\downarrow x$. Let $z \in \downarrow_{\circ} x$. Then $z \ll z$ and $z \leq x$. from Theorem 3.1 (2) $z \ll x$, i.e., $z \in \downarrow x$. Hence $\downarrow_{\circ} x \subseteq \downarrow x$. Let $l \in \downarrow x$. So $l \leq x$. Thus $\exists k \in \mathbf{K}(X)$ with $l \leq k \leq x$. from Theorem 3.1 (2), one can deduce that $k \in \downarrow_{\circ} x$. Hence $l \in \downarrow(\downarrow_{\circ} x)$. Then Proposition 2.1, $\downarrow_{\circ} x$ is directed and $\bigvee(\downarrow x) = \bigvee(\downarrow_{\circ} x)$.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors extend their appreciation to the Deanship of Scientific Research at King Khalid University for funding this work through Small Groups Project under grant number (R.G.P.1/109/44).

References

- (1) S. Abramsky and A. Jung, domain theory in the Handbook for logic in Computer Science, Volume 3, Edited by S. Abramsky, Dov M. Gabbay, and T. S. E. Maibaum, published by Clarendon Press, Oxford in 1994.
- (2) B. Branachewski and R. E. Hofmann (eds), Continuous lattices, Lecture Notes in Mathematics 871, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, 1981.
- (3) M. Erne, Scott convergence and Scott Topologies in Partially ordered sets II, in [BH] [2], pp. 61-96.
- (4) G. Gierz, K. H. Hofmann, K. Keimel, J. D. Lawson, M. Mislove, and D. s. Scott, A compendium of continuous lattices, Springer Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, 1980.
- (5) R. Heckmann, Power domain constuctions Ph. D. thesis, University Saarlandes, 1999. (<http://rwt.cs.unisb.de/heckman/diss/diss.html>.)
- (6) R. E. Hofmann, Continuous Poset completely distributive complete lattices and Hausdorff compactifications, in [3], pp. 159-208.
- (7) R. E. Hofmann, Projective sober spaces, continuous lattices, Proc. Conf., Bremen 1979, Lect. Notes Math., 871 (1981), pp. 125-158.
- (8) R. E. Hofmann, Sobrification of partially ordered sets, Semi-group Forum, Volume 17 (1979) 123-138.
- (9) R. Kummetz, Partially ordered sets with projections and their topology, pd. D. thesis; Dresden University of Technology, 2000.
- (10) K. Larsen and G. Winskel, Using information systems to solve recursive domain equations effectively, in G. Kahn, D. B. Mac-Queen and G. Plotkin, eds, Semantics of data types, Lecture Notes in Computer Science 173, Springer -Verlag, Berlin, 1984, 109-129.
- (11) J. D. Lawson, The duality of continuous posets, Houston. J. Math., Volume5, No. 3(1979) 357-386.
- (12) J. D. Lawson, The Versatile continuous order, in Lecture Notes in Computer Science 298, Springer -Verlag, Berlin, heidelberg, New Yourk, 1987, pp 134-160.
- (13) S. Lipschutz, Theory and problems of general topology, Schaum series, McJRAW-HILL INT., 1965.
- (14) G. Markowsky [1981a] , A motivation and generalization of Scott's notion of a continuous lattice, in [1979, Bremen], in [BH] [2], pp. 298-307.

- (15) J. Nino-Salcedo, On continuous posets and their applications, Ph.D. thesis, Tulane University, 1981.
- (16) S. Vickers. Information systems for continuous posets, Theoretical Computer Science 114, SIssue 2 (1993)201-299.
- (17) P. Waszhiewicz, Quantitative continuous domain, Ph.D. thesis School of Computer Science, University of Birmingham Edgbas-ton 2002.
- (18) Xiangyun Xie, Bijan Davvaz and Jian Tang, A study on (fuzzy) quasi- Γ -hyperideals in ordered Γ -semihypergroups, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems 32(6):3821-3838 · May 2017
- (19) Yanfeng Luo, Jian Tang and Asghar Khan, Characterizations of semisimple ordered semihypergroups in terms of fuzzy hyperideals, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems 30(3):1735-1753 · March 2016
- (20) Xiangyun Xie, Bijan Davvaz and Jian Tang, An investigation on hyper S-posets over ordered semihypergroups, Open Mathematics 15(1) · February 2017
- (21) H. Zhang, Dualities of domains, Ph. D. thesis, Department of Mathematics, Tulane University, 1993.

MOHAMMED M. KHALAF

HIGH INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY KING MARIOUTT, P.O. BOX 3135, EGYPT

Email address: khalfmohammed2003@yahoo.com

ESMAIL HASSAN ABDULLATIF AL-SABRI

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF SCIENCE AND ARTS, KING KHALID UNIVERSITY, MUHAYL ASSIR 61913, SAUDI ARABIA

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER, FACULTY OF SCIENCE, IBB UNIVERSITY, IBB 70270, YEMEN

Email address: esmailsabria2006@gmail.com